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First contribution to taxonomic study of macromycetes in the genus *Agaricus* from the Kou classified forest in western Burkina Faso

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ABSTRACT

In Burkina Faso, even though mycological inventories have already been carried out, very little is known about macromycetes, particularly the genus *Agaricus*. This first study of fungi of the genus *Agaricus* in the Kou classified forest aims to contribute knowledge of the local mycoflora. Based on morphological characterization, two *Agaricus* species have been reported and described. These are: *Agaricus impudicus* and *Agaricus trisulphuratus*. These two species revealed in this forest not only confirm the presence of *A. impudicus*, but also provide additional information on the distribution of *A. trisulphuratus* in the country, showing the importance of continuing inventories to enrich our knowledge of these fungi.

Keywords: *Agaricus impudicus*, *Agaricus trisulphuratus*, Morphological characterization, Kou Forest, Burkina Faso

1. INTRODUCTION

The classified Kou forest is one of the densest plant formations in Burkina Faso. It covers an area of 117 hectares and is inhabited by a diversity of species. Indeed, inventories conducted in the forest indicate a floristic wealth of around 277 species (Guinko, 2005) and a diversity of fauna (Ouédraogo *et al.*, 2011). Mycological studies have also been done on this forest, but limited to ectomycorrhizae of the genera *Russula* (Sanon *et al.*, 2014), *Amanita* (Dabiré, 2020), *Boletus* (Bakiono, 2024) and phytopathogenic polypores (Nankoné, 2022; Kusiele-Somda, 2024). As yet, few studies have looked at saprophytic macromycetes, particularly the *Agaricus* genus. Fungi of this genus are important for maintaining environmental balance, contributing to the natural decomposition of organic matter and the recycling of nutrients to benefit plants (Roux, 2006). However, they risk to disappear unknown because, in despite of its status as a forest under protected status, the Kou classified forest suffers from the adverse effects of unfavorable climates and anthropic activities, which constitute threats to the survival of the species (Yaovi *et al.*, 2021). Many fungal species are threatened with extinction. An inventory of the macromycetes of the *Agaricus* genus in this forest is needed to gain a better understanding of them and to improve our knowledge of mycological diversity. This study thus aims to highlight the presence of *Agaricus* fungi in the Kou classified forest, based on a taxonomic analysis of two *Agaricus* species collected.

2. MATERIAL METHODS

2. 1. Study area

The carpophores studied were collected between June and September of 2021 and 2022, the rainy season, in the Kou classified forest (11°10'60" N and 4°27'0" W) in western Burkina Faso (Figure 1). With a surface area of 115 ha, this forest is characterized by a south Sudanian climate (Thiombiano *et al.*, 2012) and an annual rainfall of over 1,000 mm. Its vegetation is composed of a diversity of landscapes, including forests (gallery and open) and savannahs (wooded, tree and shrub) (Guinko, 2005). The choice of this site was based on the diversity of its ecological niches, the abundance of organic matter and the presence of semi-permanent streams, creating a microclimate more favorable to the development of saprotrophic carpophores.

2. 2. Sampling

Carpophore sampling was carried out randomly at different locations in the forest. Several examples of different ages were collected, as characteristics such as the initial color of the blades, the ring and the partial veil are best seen in the young stage. Each specimen was collected completely, labeled, photographed, wrapped in aluminum foil and placed separately in a basket to avoid mixing or crushing. During collection, color variation caused by bruising, taste and odor were recorded. Geographical coordinates of all specimens were taken using a Garmin 60CS GPS.

2. 3. Macroscopic and microscopic descriptions

After the fieldwork, the macroscopic characters (shape, size, color, appearance) of the pileus, hymenium and stipe of every basidiocarp were observed with the naked eye.

These characters were noted according to the description sheet proposed by De Kesel *et al.*, (2002) and also ABC Taxa Volume 10 by Eyi *et al.*, (2011), for the imprint of vocabularies specific to mycology.

All the carpophores described were then dried using a Stockli electric dryer, packed in minigrip bags and transported to the Joseph KI-ZERBO University mycotheque, where they are conserved.

Microscopic examination was effected on dried specimens. Thin sections were taken from the hymenium, cap and stipe coatings and immersed in a 5% KOH solution for 5 to 10 minutes before being placed between slide and coverslip. Congo red was used to stain and reveal structures of hymenium elements and cystids of pileus and stipe. Melzer reagent was used for the amylose test and morphological determination of basidiospores. Microscopic characters (basidiospores, basidia, cheilocystids, pleurocystids, dermatocystids) were observed and represented using a NIKON optical microscope at $\times 13000$ zoom. Twenty (20) representatives of each microscopic element were measured on length and width using a micrometer (μm).

The quotient (Q) of the length by width of the basidiospores measured and the value of the averages (Qm) were calculated using Excel.

Figure 1. Map of the Kou classified forest.

3. RESULTS

Agaricus impudicus (Rea) Pilát, Encyclop. Mycol. 403 (1951). [Mycobank N°292273]. (Figures 2 & 3).

Pileus 3-7 cm, hemispherical, plano-convex, whitish in color, covered with dark brown scales, denser in the center and increasingly scattered towards the margin, margin slightly inflexed, with partial veil.

Flesh white, fading slightly to red or pale pink after harvesting.

Stipe, 4-8 × 0.6-1.7 cm is central, cylindrical with a bulbous base ending in a rhizomorph, smooth with a fistulous hollow internal structure, whitish in color. **Annulus** supere, concolorous with stipe, membranous, fleeting.

Lamellae tightly packed, more or less subventrous, free with smooth edges, pink when young, dark brown when mature. Fungal odor less noticeable.

Spores 4-5.86-7 × 3-3.63-5 μm (Q = 1.25-1.86-1.75 μm, n = 20), ellipsoid, elongated, ovoid, amyloid smooth without germ pores. Basidia 18-28 × 6-10 μm, tetrasporic, clavate, slightly ventral.

Basidia measure 13-27 × 7-12 μm generally tetrasporic, clavate.

Figure 2. *Agaricus impudicus*. A-C. Field photographs of the basidiomata. D. Scanning electron microphotographs of basidiospores.

Figure 3. *Agaricus impudicus*. **A:** Dermotocystids. **B:** Terminal cells of the suprapellis. **C:** Terminal subpellis cells. **D:** Basidia. **E:** Basidioles. **F:** Cheilocystids. **G:** Basidiospores.

Cheilocystids 20-45 × 10-19 μm, globose, broadly clavate, pyriform, lageniform. Solitary to gregarious fungi.

Pleurocystidia absent. Apex of terminal articles rounded.

Material examined: Burkina Faso, Houët province, Kou classified forest, N11°11'208", W004°26'487", alt. 355 cm, 08/08/2021, NRS 112 (holotype).

Comments: a species with generally gregarious basidiomes, growing mainly along roadsides or in open areas of the forest. It is not very abundant, but can appear from June to September.

Agaricus trisulphuratus Berk., Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. ser. 5, 15: 386 (1885) [Mycobank N°164564] (Figures 4 & 5).

Pileus 1.5-5 cm in diameter; conical or hemispherical when young, becoming plano-convex at maturity; curved margin; coating covered with imbricate scales; dusted with flour when touched. Its color is reddish-orange, turning to yellow-orange with age.

Stipe 3-4.5 cm long, central, smooth, fibrillose cylindrical with rhizomorphs at the base, hollow, concolored at the cap, does not discolor to the touch.

Lamellae are whitish in the initial stage, becoming brownish with age, tightly packed and free with smooth edges.

Annulus simple, situated in the upper quarter of the stipe, less persistent, of superect origin, orange color often difficult to distinguish from stipe scales.

Flesh hard, white to brownish. Fungal odor

Basidiospores measure $6-6.85-8 \times 3-3.5-4 \mu\text{m}$ with $Q = 2.67-1.50-1.99$ ($n = 20$), ellipsoid, smooth, amyloid without germinal pores.

Basidia $18-24 \times 6-10 \mu\text{m}$, tetrasporic, clavate to subclavate.

Cheilocystidia globose, fusiform, cylindrical, clavate; apex rounded, $23-31.8 \times 7-15 \mu\text{m}$.

Pleurocystidia absent. Subpellis and suprapellis hyphae cylindrical, septate.

Figure 4. *Agaricus trisulphuratus*. **A-C.** Field photographs of the basidiomata. **D.** Scanning electron microphotographs of basidiospores.

Material studied: Burkina Faso, Houët province, Kou classified forest, N11°11'297", W004°26'462", alt. 350m, 04/08/2021, NRS 093 (holotype).

Comments: *Agaricus trisulphuratus* is a species generally found in forest clearings. It is almost rare here. It generally fructifies between July and September, growing solitarily.

Figure 5. *Agaricus trisulphuratus*. **A:** Dermatocystids. **B:** Terminal cells of the suprapellis. **C:** Terminal of subpellis cells. **D:** Basidia. **E:** Basidioles. **F:** Cheilocystids. **G:** Basidiospores.

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, *Agaricus impudicus* and *Agaricus trisulphuratus* were identified on the basis of macroscopic and microscopic analyses. The specimens of *A. impudicus* described are characterized by a coating composed of regularly arranged trapezoidal scales, denser in the center; a cylindrical stipe with a bulbous base, often terminating in a mycelial cord; ellipsoidal to ovoid spores and broadly clavate subglobose cheilocystidia like those described by Cho (2020), Wasser (2000). They appear to be similar to *A. parasubrutilescens* and *A. catenariocystidiosus*, but the pileus of the latter do not discolor red after being bruised; moreover, the basidiospores of *A. impudicus* are larger than those of *A. parasubrutilescens*, which are small ($4.2-6 \times 3-3.5 \mu\text{m}$) (Dai *et al.*, 2016; Zhao *et al.*, 2016). Regarding the *A. trisulphuratus* collection, it corresponds to the specimens mentioned by Ahmad (1980), Khalid and Iqbal (1996), Zadi and Sinha (2008), Zhao *et al.*, (2016), showing orange-reddish to orange-yellow basidiocarps, with a conical then plano-convex cap covered with scales; ellipsoid, amyloid basidiospores; pleurocystids are absent. *A. trisulphuratus* can be confused with *Agaricus crocopenplus*, but the latter can be distinguished by the presence of a distinct white ring (Premarathne *et al.*, 2025), whereas the ring of *A. trisulphuratus* is orange, often difficult to differentiate from the stipe scales. Confusion is also possible with *Agaricus erythrotrichus*, but this species has much larger basidiospores ($6.2-7.4 \times 3.8-4.3 \mu\text{m}$), with upright, pointed flakes in the center of the pilus (Heinemann, 1956b). These two agarics species have already been reported in Africa, notably in Togo (Zhao *et al.*, 2011). But *A. trisulphuratus* is also known from Tanzania (Berkeley, 1885) and South Africa (Kinge *et al.*, 2020). In Burkina Faso, previous investigations have revealed the presence of *A. trisulphuratus* in the Kaboré Tambi National Park and in the Niangoloko and Tiogo classified forests (Guissou, 2005). *Agaricus impudicus*, on the other hand, had not yet been included in the country's mycological inventories. Its discovery in the Kou classified forest, following this study, constitutes an important contribution to the enrichment of the fungal flora of Burkina Faso.

5. CONCLUSION

The study of Agarics in the Kou Classified Forest, enabled us to inventory and carry out an anatomical and morphological analysis of two agaric species, *A. impudicus* and *A. trisulphuratus*. This work strengthens our knowledge of the fungal diversity of this forest. It also confirms the presence of *A. impudicus* and provides new information on the distribution of *A. trisulphuratus* in Burkina Faso, highlighting the importance of continuing inventories to improve our understanding of these fungi.

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